

Port of Antwerpen (BE)

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the port of Antwerpen (BE) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the port area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the port (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), population living in the WS within 10 km from the port, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the port and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes. The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

Port of Antwerpen (BE)

Port area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the port within 5 and 10 km

Port area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the port within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., Monge, S. & González Ortiz, A. (2025). Air quality around ports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/12, version 2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416089>).
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European Environment Agency
European Topic Centre
Human health and the environment

NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Belgium	BETR822	Industrial	51.26	4.34	29.73		0.00	SE	129,424
Belgium	BELAT44	Background	51.29	4.35	27.32		0.00	NE	31,454
Belgium	BETR891	Industrial	51.26	4.39	24.08		0.00	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETR892	Industrial	51.26	4.28	21.54	-34.69	0.00	SW	28,898
Belgium	BETR897	Industrial	51.25	4.34	22.11	-34.49	0.00	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETM802	Industrial	51.26	4.42	21.71	-56.09	0.00	E	62,256
Belgium	BETR803	Background	51.23	4.43	20.00		0.30	SE	129,424
Belgium	BELAL01	Industrial	51.24	4.39	16.25		0.50	SE	129,424
Belgium	BELAT83	Industrial	51.34	4.30	25.04		0.56	N	9,776
Belgium	BETR806	Traffic	51.22	4.42	28.94		0.57	SE	129,424

NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Belgium	BELSA08	Industrial	51.33	4.36	18.59		0.99	NE	31,454
Belgium	BETR830	Industrial	51.32	4.26	18.80	-28.94	1.19	NW	282
Belgium	BETR818	Industrial	51.21	4.35	18.28		1.43	S	24,973
Belgium	BETR831	Industrial	51.35	4.34	19.45	-49.99	1.58	N	9,776

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Belgium	BETM802	Industrial	51.26	4.42	11.04		0.00	E	62,256
Belgium	BETR822	Industrial	51.26	4.34	14.21		0.00	SE	129,424
Belgium	BELAL05	Industrial	51.26	4.28	10.13		0.00	SW	28,898
Belgium	BETDU07	Industrial	51.23	4.45	10.48		0.17	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETR803	Background	51.23	4.43	11.18		0.30	SE	129,424
Belgium	BELAL01	Industrial	51.24	4.39	10.26		0.50	SE	129,424
Belgium	BELAL04	Industrial	51.29	4.29	10.16		0.51	NW	282
Belgium	BELAT83	Industrial	51.34	4.30	9.45		0.56	N	9,776
Belgium	BELAL03	Industrial	51.25	4.20	10.56	-54.13	0.88	W	3,818
Belgium	BELAL02	Industrial	51.30	4.23	10.73		1.37	NW	282

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PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Belgium	BETR818	Industrial	51.21	4.35	10.11		1.43	S	24,973
Belgium	BETAL10	Industrial	51.22	4.37	9.91		1.60	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETAL09	Industrial	51.22	4.37	9.81		1.60	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETR801	Background	51.21	4.43	10.58	-43.31	1.91	SE	129,424
Belgium	BEGR801	Background	51.21	4.43	9.32	-62.47	1.91	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETR802	Traffic	51.21	4.43	11.15	-47.94	1.94	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETR804	Traffic	51.21	4.44	9.90		2.02	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETR805	Traffic	51.21	4.42	11.88		2.14	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETZD08	Industrial	51.23	4.33	10.09		2.38	S	24,973
Belgium	BETZD01	Industrial	51.22	4.33	10.86		2.46	S	24,973

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 3)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Belgium	BELHB23	Industrial	51.17	4.34	9.64		2.58	S	24,973
Belgium	BELSA04	Industrial	51.31	4.40	10.12		3.22	NE	31,454
Belgium	BETR817	Background	51.18	4.42	9.99		4.00	SE	129,424
Belgium	BETR823	Background	51.21	4.24	10.36		4.02	SW	28,898
Belgium	BETR811	Background	51.25	4.49	10.45		4.15	E	62,256
Belgium	BEGR811	Background	51.25	4.49	8.58	-60.94	4.15	E	62,256

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Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

- High density residential
- Low density residential
- Industry
- Traffic
- Agricultural areas
- Natural areas

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